

HOW TO TEACH SPEAKING: LINGUISTIC KNOWLEDGE

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A language achieves a genuinely global status when it develops a special role that is recognized in every country. This might seem like stating the obvious, but it is not, for the notion of “special role” has many facets. Such a role will be most evident in countries where large numbers of the people speak the language. In this article authors shows the English as a global language as a mother tongue – in the case of English, this would be mean the USA, Canada, Britain, Ireland, Australia, New Zealand, South Africa, several Caribbean countries and a sprinkling of other territories.

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To achieve such a status, a language has to be taken by other countries around the world. Because of the three-pronged development- of first-language, second-language, and foreign-language speakers – it is inevitable that a global language will eventually come to be used by more people than any other language. English has already reached this stage in our country too. Our Universities teach this language to the specialists in all spheres, especially to the military servicemen.

Linguistic knowledge is often ranged along a cline from the big picture, e.g. knowledge of the way an anecdote typically unfolds, to the fine print, e/g/ knowledge of grammar and vocabulary. In fact, the boundaries between categories are blurred, and they work interdependently, such that in reality it is difficult to account for particular features of a speech event by reference to any single knowledge system.[1] However, for convenience, we shall discuss these different levels in turn.

Genre knowledge

Very broadly, there are two main purposes for speaking. Speaking serves either a transactional function, in that its primary purpose is to convey information and facilitate the exchange of goods or services, or it serves an interpersonal function, in that its primary purpose is to establish and maintain social relations. A typical transactional speech event might be phoning to book a table at a restaurant. The story that Lath tells about her domestic science class is motivated less by the need to convey the facts of the matter (i.e. a transactional purpose) than by the wish to amuse her audience and thereby maintain a sense of shared community between friends (i.e. an interpersonal purpose).[2]

These two basic purposes for speaking generate a host of different types of speech events. These, in turn, will be sequenced and structured in accordance with the kinds of social and mental processes that they accompany. We saw for example, how Kath told her kedgere story according to a narrative script, which, to put it very simply, has a beginning, middle, and end.

Service encounters, such as buying goods, getting information, or requesting a service, are transactional speech events that follow a fairly predictable script. Typically, the exchange begins with a greeting,

followed by an offer, followed by a request, and so on, as in: [3]

<p>Good morning. Good morning. What would you like? A dozen eggs, please. Anything else?... etc.</p>

A certain amount of variation is generally permitted; some of the moves may be dispensable, while others of a more interpersonal nature – such as a comment about the weather – might be optional. Different cultures and sub-cultures may develop their own variants. Some service encounters in some cultures may permit bargaining, for example.

Over time and within particular speech communities, certain, ways of realizing these speech events have become conventionalized to the point that they have evolved into specific genres. Genre is an elusive term. Here we will use it to mean simply a type of speech event, especially in terms of how that speech event might be labeled by its participants. Hence, there is a difference between saying “I had a chat with the boss” and “I had a job interview with the boss” or “I did a presentation to the boss”. Knowledge of how specific genres –such as chatting, job interviews, or business presentations- are realized is part of the linguistic knowledge that speakers in a particular speech community share.

An important factor that determines the structure of a genre is whether it is interactive or non-interactive. Multi-party speech, as in a shopping exchange or casual conversation between friends, is jointly constructed and interactive. Monologues, such as television journalists live report, a university lecture, or when you leave a voice-mail message, are non-interactive.

Finally, a distinction needs to be made between planned and unplanned speech. Certain speech genres, such as public speeches and business presentations, are typically planned, to the point that they might be completely scripted in advance. This means that their linguistic features will resemble or replicate features of written language. On the other hand, a phone conversa-

tion to ask for train timetable information, while following a predictable sequence, is normally not planned in advance: each participant has to make strategic and spontaneous decisions on the basis of the way the discourse unfolds. This, in turn, will affect the kind of language used.

On the basis of these criteria, we can classify speaking genres according to their general purposes, the kind of participation they involve, and the degree of planning (bearing in mind that these distinctions are less polarities than stages on a continuum). For example: [4]

	purpose	participation	planning
Airport announcements	transactional	Non-interactive	planned
Sports commentary	transactional	Non-interactive	unplanned
Job interview	transactional	interactive	(partly) planned
Service encounter	transactional	(partly) interactive	
Leaving a voice-mail message	Transactional or interpersonal	Non-interactive	unplanned
Casual conversation	interpersonal	interactive	unplanned
Joke telling	interpersonal	(partly) interactive	(partly) planned

Conclusion

We started this article by making a distinction between what speakers can do- that is the mental and physiological processes involved in speaking – and what speakers know –that is the knowledge base that speakers draw on that enables these processes.

The kinds of knowledge that speakers bring to the skill of speaking comprise extra linguistic knowledge, such as background knowledge of topic and culture, and linguistic knowledge, including discourse knowledge, speech act knowledge, and knowledge of grammar, vocabulary, and phonology.

So we have described speaking skills and speaker knowledge insofar as they relate to highly-skilled, knowledgeable speakers, making no distinction between speaking in a first or a second or third, or fourth

etc. language. But speakers of another language do not, initially, have easy access to these skills and this knowledge.

References

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